

A WAY-OUT OF EPISTEMOLOGY: JEWISH IDENTITY IN THE THIRTEENTH TRIBE

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ABSTRACT

Arthur Koestler in his historical book, *The Thirteenth Tribe*, narrates how a nation lost the name of Khazars and became known as Jews. He describes how at ninth and tenth centuries, the rise of Rus power had a direct impact on the Khazars and the map of Europe. With this, he describes how the Khazar Kingdom disintegrated and fell into pieces and the majority, merged with other close people. *The Thirteenth Tribe* is a well written and researched book that provided insightful anecdotes when documentary evidence was lacking. But the reader should be open to divergent views of the history of the peoples in question. Koestler made a good case for his hypothesis and presented this in a concise with stories within the past. This study, expounds how Koestler supports Israel while he doubts whether the Zionist Jews are the original Jews or not.

Keywords: Arthur Koestler, *The Thirteenth Tribe*, Identity, Khazar Kingdom, Judaism, Ashkenazi Jews

INTRODUCTION

Arthur Koestler (1905-83) is a Jewish writer and scholar, from Hungarian and Austrian parents. Shortly before the Second World War, he became a refugee in England. Koestler learned English, German, Spanish, Russian, Hebrew, and French to study quickly and explore various European communities and cultures, due to his explorer spirit. He read up on Zionism when he was psychology student at Vienna University and became a member of a Zionist Party. In his youth, the excitement of the illusory aspirations of Zionism transformed him into one of the pioneers of the Jewish emigrants to Palestine. He went to Jerusalem and Tel Aviv but suffered a hard life, and because of famishment, he was almost in death, and later, he went to Berlin to work on the press. Casteller's life routine was in different ups and downs until 1938. Koestler first became a member of the Communist Party in Germany. Traveling from Ukraine and Central Asia to Baku and the borders of Afghanistan, he even visited former Soviet leaders in Moscow. Afterward, in the aftermath of the experience that he had gained, the Jewish Promised Paradise concealed the Communists and found anti-communism and went Europe to London, where he wrote the novel *Darkness at Noon* (1940) against disillusionment with Stalin and the Soviet Union's version of Communism at the outset of World War II, using the information he collected. However, like many other intellectuals in the 1930s, Koestler saw the only hope and alternative to fascism in the Soviet experiment. He became a member of the Communist Party in 1931 but left it in 1938. After the Second World War, Koestler became a British citizen and all his books since 1940 published in English. Then, with the pen of penetration, he saved millions of people in suspicion

and unheeded from falling into the trap of communists. In his sophistication, he became one of the critics of Zionist ideals and criticized the mythology of “the purity of the Jewish race.” His death is controversial; of course. What has been reflected was his illness and his attempt to suicided with his third wife, Sinita. But some other historians believe that both cancer and Parkinson were not the reason for this decision, but he is killed to author *The Thirteenth Tribe: The Khazar Empire and its Heritage* (1976). Despite he could not tolerate Parkinson’s harassment, but apparently, begetters thought that the first poison had not been affected, and the second poison had been given to him, but later noticed that both had worked.

A Forgotten Turkish Empire

Koestler starts *The Thirteenth Tribe* with stories beyond the history. From the seventh to the tenth centuries, Europe—to the West by the Black Sea, and to the East by the Khazar Sea or the Caspian Sea—were ruled by a Jewish state, known as the Khazar Empire. Origin of the name is derived from the Turkish root “gaz,” means “to wander,” and “nomad,” also German word “Ketzer” that means Jew or heretic. (Koestler, 1978) Yakubi, the Arab historian of the ninth century, declares that the “origin of the Khazars back to Japheth, third son of Noah. The Japheth motive frequently recurs in the literature, while others connect them with Abraham or Alexander the Great.” (Koestler, 1978) In fact, people were Turkish stock. First Turkish state lasted for a century (AD. 550-650) and then fell apart, then the name “Turk” was used to apply to a specific nation, as distinct from other Turkic-speaking peoples like the Khazars and Bulgars, then the Persians and Byzantines came to call them “Kingdom of the North.” (Koestler, 1978).

The culture of the Khazars, a dominant but almost forgotten power in Eastern Europe that adopted Judaism over a millennium before being destroyed by Genghis Khan (1162 – 1227), the founder of the Mongol Empire is an intriguing subject worth to study. It is unfortunate that there are not enough manuscripts about the Khazars. Koestler proves, beyond doubt, that modern Jews are not Biblical Israelites. There appears to be more material available today than the time Koestler wrote his book, but the world is still waiting for a weighty book that addresses the Khazars’ origin and what a medieval Jewish kingdom appears. *The Thirteenth Tribe* is well written and researched book which provided insightful anecdotes when documentary evidence was lacking. Anyone interested in reading this book should have a better understanding of the history than average Jewish people, their diaspora and recent situation of the Central Asian tribal groups, Western Europe, and of the Byzantine Empire. The reader should be open to divergent views of the history of the peoples in question. Admittedly, Koestler made a good case for his hypothesis and presented this in a concise.

Koestler was not anti-Semite; however, his book has long been a favorite among neo-Nazis who use it to claim that the people identified as European Jews are not the descendants of the people mentioned in the Bible, making it tolerable to hate them and kill them en masse. A highly popular modern European theory returns to the middle nineteenth century which serves that the Jews around Europe were not the same as those of the Hebrew Bible, thus disassociating European Jews from and tinging European Jews with various vogue stereotypes applied against Asians. Dimitry Obolensky, Professor of Russian History at the University of Oxford admits “The main contribution of the Khazars to world history was their success in holding the line of the Caucasus against the northward onslaught of the Arabs.” (Koestler, 1978) Khazarian armies blocked the armies of the Caliphate Arab Muslims after the death of Muhammad, the Prophet (570-632 A.D) conquest of Eastern Europe. They possessed a critical position at the vital gateway between the

Black Sea and the Caspian, or concisely between the tremendous eastern powers, for a century and a half, and blocking the gateway from Asia into Europe: “Khazaria was by no means isolated from the civilized world; compared to its tribal neighbours in the north it was a cosmopolitan country, open to all sorts of cultural and religious influences.” (Koestler, 1978)

Koestler’s book does a great job of shining light on a historical era of the Jewish community which composes 0.2% of the world’s population. Arthur Koestler, himself, was born in 1905 in Budapest. Though he studied science and psychology in Vienna at the age of twenty, he became a foreign correspondent and worked for various European newspapers in the Middle East, Paris, Berlin, Russia, and Spain. Koestler, as a Hungarian Jew himself, was particularly interested in the role the Khazars played in the founding of the Hungarian nation; a fact which later led to the tragedy of 1944, when the Nazis exterminated over half a million Hungarian Jews, who were virtually indistinguishable from their Christian neighbors. Despite the fact that these figures are suppositions, are not proven, and are in doubt with historians. Mahmoud Ahmadinejad, the former president of the Islamic Republic of Iran, also suggested fundamental research about the number of the people were killed in the Holocaust. (Vick, Karl, 2005)

At eighth and ninth centuries, the world was polarized between the two super-powers representing Christianity (Roman Emperor), Islam (Caliph of Baghdad), and the Khazar Empire, independent by accepting neither Christianity nor Islam. Many Jews, Koestler declares, fled Rome and Greece to Khazaria to avoid forced conversion to Christianity. They adopted Islam when forced. Al-Masudi, a historian, inscribed “At the time of Harun al Rashid, the Byzantine Emperor forced the Jews to emigrate; these emigrants came to the Khazar country where they found an intelligent but uneducated race to whom they offered their religion. The natives found it better than their own and accepted it.” (Koestler, 1978) Koestler disproves the idea of a Jewish ‘race.’ Additionally, he says that most Jews of contemporary did not originate from Palestine and are not even of Semitic origin. That group of people there and became Jews through conversion, were on the order of their king. “The bulk of modern Jewry is not of Palestinian, but of Caucasian origin.” Koestler continues: “The mainstream of Jewish migrations did not flow from the Mediterranean across France and Germany to the east and then back again. The stream moved in a consistently western direction, from the Caucasus, from the Ukraine into Poland and thence into Central Europe.” (Koestler, 1978)

Koestler in his historical book states how a nation lost the name of Khazars and became known as Jews. He describes how at ninth and tenth centuries, the rise of Rus power had a direct impact on the Khazars and the map of Europe. The Khazar kingdom disintegrated and fell into pieces, and the majority merged with other related peoples. So Khazar rulers felt emotionally committed to the fate of Jews in other parts of the world: “The Khazars, after the defeat by the Russians in 965, lost their empire but retained their independence within narrower frontiers, and their Judaic faith, well into the 13th Century.” (Koestler, 1978) During this era, the relation between Magyars, the Hungarian nation, and Khazars became even closer for two reasons: First of all, the Khazars gave them a king, who founded the first Magyar dynasty. Moreover, several Khazar tribes joined the Magyars and profoundly transformed their ethnic character. That is why the biblically minded Slavonic epics speak of “Jews,” rather than Khazars.

The prophets may thunder against ‘marrying daughters of a strange god,’ yet the promiscuous Israelites were not deterred, and their leaders were foremost in giving a bad example. Even the first patriarch, Abraham, cohabited with Hagar, an Egyptian; Joseph

married Asenath, who was not only Egyptian but the daughter of a priest; Moses married a Midianite, Zipporah; Samson, the Jewish hero, was a Philistine; King David's mother was a Moabite, and he married a princess of Geshur; as for King Solomon, whose mother was a Hittite... (Koestler, 1978)

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From the anthropologist's point of view, regard to physical characteristics shows a greater similarity between Jews and their Gentile host-nation than between Jews living in different countries. It ignores the fact that features regarded as typically Jewish by comparison with Nordic people cease to appear so in a Mediterranean environment; it is unaware of the impact of the social environment on physique and countenance; and it confuses biological with social inheritance. (Koestler, 1978)

Another reason is contrary to the assumption that the Eastern Jews have been French and the Rhine, and this is because the Yiddish language was spoken by the majority of the Jewish masses of Eastern Europe. Millions of Jews had already spoken it, and now their survivors in the USSR and the United States have kept that language. Indeed, Yiddish is a strange potion from the mixing of the Hebrew and Germanic languages of the Middle Ages and other Slavic elements and is written on the Hebrew line which today is fell into oblivion. Some Western linguists considered it as one of the distracting dialects. Koestler's opponents have one more observation about *The Thirteenth Tribe*. They articulate, in the nineteenth century, Jews had no proof to challenge this theory. The best contradictory evidence is linguistic because neither Hebrew nor Yiddish seems to contain any trace of a central Asian language. Now, with genetic evidence, we can positively identify common ancestry of Jews from areas as far-flung as Germany, Spain, Yemen, and Russia. Common Y chromosome can be found among members of every community, and the genetic migration maps reflect little Turkic input. While it, some Khazars may be married into the broader Jewish community. The evidence indicates that it never happened in overwhelming number. Indeed, there are considerable historical shreds of evidence that the Khazar were mostly cut off from the rest of the Jewish world. The other idea says that many European Jews, show non-middle Eastern features like blue eyes, blond hair, etc. However, the existence of large-scale conversion to Judaism is a clear historical fact, mainly before the time Christianity became firmly rooted in Eastern and South Eastern Europe.

An Excession to Twelve Early Tribes

Koestler, referring to the Khazarian case, deliberately calls it the "thirteenth tribe" (in addition to the twelve early tribes of the Israelites), as well as other documents. He rejects the Jewish race's purity and states that a Jew can not be a specific race, and the only thing that distinguishes a Jew from non-Jews is the issue of religion. In his view, the race of the Jews is not genuine, and the Jews nowadays are not of the same generation as the Israelites. For him, the race of Jews is mixed with races like the Caspian Turks. He says the Jewish people of Europe who now burst in 'the return to Palestine, the Promised Land,' are not at all Palestinian and originally Jewish, and have no historical or racial right to the Palestinian land. There were from the Caspian Turks who lived in the northern part of the Caspian Sea or the sea of Qazvin. Later, they left the Caspian region to Europe for historical and political reasons, and chose the Jewish religion for political reasons, despite some of them were Jews before heading to Europe. But today, without regard to their true history, they have sneaked out of Europe for 'Palestine as their ancestral home.' From Kessler's point of view, they do not have the right to return to the Promised Land. They were

Caspian people and later converted to the Jewish religion. Considering the right to return to the Promised Land (Palestine), Palestinian Oriental Jews only consist a minority. It worth-emphasizing that the same Eastern Jews, centuries ago, have emigrated from Palestine to trade and other purposes and have chosen different nationalities and abolished such a right.

From the historical perspective, he points out that the Jews or the Israelites consist of twelve tribes that are related to the descendants of Jacob, the third Hebrew progenitor with whom God made a covenant. But in the meantime, from the perspective of historians such as Koestler, former Caspian people are the people who try to enter into the crew of these twelve tribes in any way. Therefore, in their view, they are the thirteenth tribe, and they are not originated from the Sons of Israelites. In *The Thirteenth Tribe*, Koestler has expanded heritage, social, political, historical, and cultural heritage in a documented book regulated based on scientific principles and foundations.

At the beginning of the sixth chapter, Koestler indicates two essential clear facts: First, the disappearance of the Caspian nation from its historical habitat; Second, the emergence of the most massive gathering centers of Jews in the adjacent areas of the Caspian region in Eastern Europe and the process of their formation. Naturally, these two events are interconnected, and historians believe that the Caspian migration has led to the rise of Judaism in Poland, but the extent of the impact of immigration is unclear. Later, Koestler, concludes in the final analysis:

Thus we are made to realize that the Jewish community in the German Rhineland was numerically small, even before the First Crusade, and had shrunk to even smaller proportions after having gone through the winepress of the Lord. Yet east of the Rhine, in central and northern Germany, there were as yet no Jewish communities at all, and none for a long time to come. The traditional conception of Jewish historians that the Crusade of 1096 swept like a broom a mass-migration of German Jews into Poland is simply a legend—or rather an ad hoc hypothesis invented because, as they knew little of Khazar history, they could see no other way to account for the emergence, out of nowhere, of this unprecedented concentration of Jews in Eastern Europe. Yet there is not a single mention in the contemporary sources of any migration, large or small, from the Rhineland further east into Germany, not to mention distant Poland. (Koestler, 1978)

CONCLUSION

The primary aim of Koestler by writing *The Thirteenth Tribe: The Khazar Empire and its Heritage* is ponderous. Koestler supported Israel at the very end of his book in Appendix IV. He asserted that the concern of the Zionist Jews about the original Jews “...is irrelevant, and cannot affect Israel’s right to exist.” (Koestler, 1978) They are few lines before another statement that says: “...that right is not based on the hypothetical origins of the Jewish people, nor on the mythological covenant of Abraham with God; it is based on international law — i.e., on the United Nations’ decision in 1947 to partition Palestine, once a Turkish province, then a British Mandated Territory, into an Arab and a Jewish State.” (Koestler, 1978) David Cesarani in his book *Arthur Koestler: The Homeless Mind* proclaims this subject in another way. He utters Koestler “wanted to be a Jew, albeit on his peculiar terms.” (Cesarani, 1999). Koestler discusses the deportation of the Caspian during their weak years. A large part of them went to Poland and Liechtenstein, Hungary and the Balkans, and formed the Jewish community of Eastern Europe, which is the vast majority of the Jewish community in the world. Of course, one can make this

a form that such a discussion in history cannot be denied or even prove something. In answer, Koestler has examined various aspects and dimensions to clarify the issue and is the only controversy with these ethnographic materials. Besides, it has come to a close, although ultimately that the conclusion is fair to the reader.

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